

A Review of Current Applications of Artificial Intelligence in Renewable Energy

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Abstract—The utilisation of renewable energy, especially solar and wind energy, has increased drastically in the past few years. At the same time, AI also revolutionises the world in every sector. This paper aims to provide the current use of AI in the field of renewable energy, such as wind energy, solar energy, as well as focus on the prediction, distribution of energy and efficiency of the system. There are various AI techniques used such as Machine Learning, Deep Learning, to improve the accuracy of forecasting, also for managing complex data. This paper provides the actual use of AI in the real world in the renewable energy sector, different tools and the latest advancements of AI for maximum utilisation the renewable energy. This review also provides current challenges for AI-driven renewable energy systems.

Keywords—Artificial Intelligence (AI), Renewable Energy, Energy Prediction, Energy Distribution, Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Forecasting, AI Applications

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, Global warming and climate change have become paramount problems; also, the high consumption of fossil fuels can lead to a transition towards renewable energy sources. Furthermore, wind and solar energies are considered the best alternative, and these are being widely adopted by the world in recent times. These sources are not only clean and sustainable, but they also reduce carbon emissions. Having said that, these sources are very unpredictable because these sources are highly dependent on several environmental factors. Therefore, to analyse and manage them is quite challenging. For example, integration of the grids as well as management of efficient power.

To fight back against these challenges, Artificial Intelligence(AI) can play a pivotal role in enhancing renewable energy systems' performance and reliability. AI provides well-structured decision-making with data-driven algorithms and models. Various techniques, such as Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL), are considered very effective in renewable energy systems to improve forecasting accuracy and provide real-time control to manage it.

The involvement of AI in the renewable energy sector has made lots of things very easy, such as smart grid functions. Efficient energy storage and automatic maintenance of the systems. Besides this, the improvement in forecasting, load balancing, and fault detection in renewable energy systems is made possible by the availability of sensor data and advanced computing and AI models, which are collecting real-time data and also analysing historical data. As a consequence, it reduces the cost of the operations.

First and foremost, Lago et al. [1] reviewed that neural networks and support vector regression provided better outcomes for the prediction of solar and wind power. The study found that AI-driven models perform better in terms of accuracy compared to traditional statistical methods. The study mainly focuses on time series input and the importance of feature selection to improve the prediction capacity of AI models.

Secondly, Ahmad et al. [2] discussed the use of AI, like how AI is used in the sustainable energy industry, the role of AI in the management of the grid, optimisation techniques of energy distribution, and renewable energy forecasting. The author emphasised Reinforcement Learning techniques, making dynamic decision-making very easy in an uncertain energy environment.

Next, Bedi et al. [3] demonstrated predicting solar power generation using frameworks of Deep Learning. In their experiment, they found that Long Short-Term Memory networks are better for capturing the temporal dependencies of solar irradiance data compared to conventional time-series models.

Kaung Myat San et al. [4] contributed to wind energy forecasting with a hybrid model of AI. The study covered how regression algorithms and Convolutional Neural Networks are used for processing temporal and spatial data. As a result, this approach is very useful to improve the accuracy of forecasting in the wind farms, especially are situated near the sea.

Moreover, Malik Ali Judge et al. [5] depicted how to implement AI in smart grid fault detection. Lastly, Dina A. Elalfy et al. [6] described how we can use AI for energy storage systems by optimising battery management through AI algorithms.

II. APPLICATIONS OF AI IN RENEWABLE ENERGY

II. 1. PLANNING AND INTERCONNECTION OF GRID

In the past few years, the integration of the power grid and renewable energy has been quite a slow process. As a consequence, it took many years to perform feasibility studies. However, after the introduction of AI, this thing is transforming very rapidly. In 2025, the partnerships between Google and Tapestry with the U.S. grid operator PJM implement AI-based models to increase the interconnection planning, and it is decided as a game changer, reducing waiting time from 37-38 months to 14-15 months by analysing a large dataset of past project applications. Likewise, the AI4IX program was also launched by the U.S. Department of Energy with funding of approximately \$30 million for supporting AI adoption in grid planning.

II. 2. WEATHER PREDICTION AND RENEWABLE OUTPUT FORECASTING

The renewable energy sources, like solar, wind, are highly dependent on the condition of the weather. Therefore, to balance energy and for planning, we require accurate weather forecasting. Traditional numerical weather prediction models are very powerful, but they require high computational power. Currently, the new AI models like PVNet and CloudCast have shown significant improvements in forecasting solar irradiance. Basically, the prediction is provided using the images from satellites, previous data, and movement patterns of clouds, and these models predict solar energy output up to 24-48 hours in advance. Energy dispatching and load scheduling have become better due to the deployment of these models in India and the UK, with 40% improved accuracy. Furthermore, other models like Aardvark are highly suitable for resource-constrained regions because they use architecture of lightweight neural architecture, which consumes less energy and provides very fast predictions.

II. 3. WIND ENERGY OPTIMISATION AND DISPATCH

An AI model of DeepMind uses previous data of turbine and weather conditions to predict 36 hours in advance for wind energy output. In the U.S., this model escalated its 20% economic value during the field test by recommending optimal bidding strategies, which are based on predicted generation. As a result, it makes wind energy projects more financially sustainable. Khan et al developed a hybrid model that processes spatial and temporal wind data, and improves prediction accuracy specifically for the offshore wind farms by integrating Convolutional Neural Networks with regression techniques.

II. 4. SMART GRID MANAGEMENT AND LOAD BALANCING

AI plays an essential role in the smart grid to make instant decision-making in energy distribution. Moreover, Machine Learning is also useful for detecting consumption patterns, activating on-demand response actions. In 2024, to balance loads during peak usage hours, effectively preventing grid overloads and reducing blackouts, an AI-based system was deployed in some regions of Europe and Asia. Also, these systems continuously monitor grid health using the sensor network and SCADA data, which enhances fault detection.

II. 5. ENERGY STORAGE AND BATTERY OPTIMISATION

Battery life and efficiency are the biggest concerns; however, AI is really trying to optimise charging and predict battery degradation, and improve energy storage management. In 2023, Graph Networks for Materials Exploration forecasted approximately 380000 latest materials, which are highly beneficial for new battery chemistries with higher energy density. Orbital Materials uses AI for designing novel electrolytes and electrode materials that are useful for lithium-ion and sodium-ion batteries. Moreover, Fluence and Tesla use battery management systems that are completely operated by AI, and it is used in controlling large storage farms.

II. 6. MAINTENANCE, FAULT DETECTION, AND ASSET MANAGEMENT

For advanced prediction, AI uses real-time sensor data from solar panels, turbines. In 2024, Al Mamun et al. described that faults in smart grids could be detected by the machine learning model with approximately accuracy of approximately 95% and it reduces operational costs as well as extends the lifespan of the equipment used in this sector. Image recognition algorithms in drones are also being used to inspect solar farms and wind turbines, identifying cracks, soiling.

II.7. ENERGY TRADING AND MARKET OPTIMISATION

AI models help to make decisions about when to buy or sell energy by analysing market trends, prices, weather patterns, and grid data. Lots of companies are using reinforcement learning agents to maximise profit and maintain grid balance in 2024.. For example, European energy trading firms started using AI to predict market prices and optimise renewable generation portfolios. These systems are highly beneficial for them and they increased profit up to 10-15 % also providing stability in the market.

Table 1: Recent Applications of AI in Renewable Energy

Field	AI technique
Grid Interconnection	Predictive ML, Optimization AI
Solar Forecasting	CNN, Deep Learning (PVNet)
Wind Energy Dispatch	Time-Series AI, Deep RL
Battery Management	Graph AI, ML Optimization
Smart Grid Fault Detection	Supervised ML
Maintenance (Drones + AI)	Image Recognition, Object Detection
Energy Trading	Reinforcement Learning

Figure 1: AI Integration Across the Renewable Energy Lifecycle

III. CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS IN RENEWABLE ENERGY

Artificial Intelligence has lots of potential. Having said that, implementing AI in renewable energy systems is quite challenging. It contains limitations in technical, infrastructural and organisational domains.

III. 1. DATA AVAILABILITY AND QUALITY

The biggest challenge in the AI field is the large amount of dirty, unstructured, and missing data. Generally, AI requires clean, labelled, reliable data to achieve accuracy in the AI-based models. However, in the renewable energy domain, sensors collect real-time data from solar panels, turbines, and grids, which are often noisy, incomplete. If we get an example of some developing countries, where the data collection infrastructure is quite poor. Admittedly, some past data sets are sometimes not accessible, which causes limitations on developing a generalised model. Without the availability of correct and sufficient data, it is very difficult to achieve accuracy in the model.

III. 2. COMPUTATIONAL DEMAND AND INFRASTRUCTURE

Deep Learning, Reinforcement Learning, Generative AI, etc., these are the advanced models of AI that require very high computational resources. Also, running these models in a real-time environment, such as a wind dispatch system or grids, requires a high-performance computing infrastructure with powerful GPU acceleration and cloud access. Furthermore, renewable energy plants are also installed far from the city centre, generally in rural or remote areas, which requires all of the necessary resources to be added at a particular place, which is more costly.

III. 3. MODEL INTERPRETABILITY AND TRUST

AI algorithms, for example, deep neural networks, operate as black boxes; therefore, in domains like energy, it limits the trust of the stakeholders because, in deep neural networks, humans can't easily interpret the decision-making process. Engineers need to understand the basis of every recommendation by AI for making decisions.

III. 4. INTEGRATION WITH ENERGY SYSTEMS

To integrate AI with the energy systems, especially the traditional systems, creates a challenge in terms of compatibility, data acquisition, and control logic. For instance, modern sensor networks or data output formats are not supported by the older turbines, transformers, which lead to advanced AI model training and deployment.

III. 5. CYBERSECURITY AND DATA PRIVACY

AI systems are heavily reliant on cloud platforms and real-time data, which leads to potential cybersecurity threats. Massive energy disruptions, economic losses, or even safety hazards can occur due to a cyberattack on an AI-based smart power grid or battery management system. Moreover, there are lots of concerns regarding the privacy of user data consumption.

III. 6. SHORTAGE OF SKILLED WORKFORCE

Maintaining and deploying the AI system requires expertise that includes knowledge of multiple domains - energy systems, AI, ML, DL, electronics cybersecurity.

Having said that, right now, there is a shortage of professionals who contains all of these skill sets. Therefore, many organisations rely on the available generic tools, which are actually not suited for the energy domain.

Table 2: Summary of Technical and Organisational Challenges in Implementing AI in Renewable Energy Systems.

Challenge	Impact
Data Availability & Quality	Reduce prediction accuracy
High Computational Requirements	Limited scalability in remote regions
Model Interpretability	Low stakeholder trust
Legacy System Integration	High retrofitting costs and delays
Cybersecurity Risks	Threat to grid stability and privacy
Shortage of Skilled Workforce	Slows down deployment and innovation

IV. FUTURE SCOPE OF AI IN RENEWABLE ENERGY

IV. 1. EXPLAINABLE AI

Many functions of Deep Learning and complex Machine Learning models are very difficult to understand for making decisions or predictions. This is one of the most significant concerns of this field, where accountability and transparency are critical. Furthermore, future research is expected to focus on high accuracy and interpretability, explainable AI development. These models would allow validation of decision-making of AI, particularly in grid control, fault detection and demand response.

IV. 2. EDGE AI

In Edge AI, models are executed and deployed on local hardware rather than depending on cloud computing and high-speed internet access. Edge AI is really beneficial for decentralised energy generation and in off-grid or remote locations such as rooftop solar, rural wind farms, and microgrids. Future research will focus on energy-efficient and lightweight AI algorithms for edge devices. These edge devices reduce latency and dependency on external infrastructure by making real-time decisions for power management and energy optimisation locally.

IV. 3. GENERATIVE AI

Large language models and deep generative network models of Generative AI are widely used for complex simulations and energy system prediction. For example, the GNoME model can predict approximately 380000 inorganic compounds that are useful for next-generation solar materials and battery technologies. In the future, generative AI will play a pivotal role in simulating climate conditions, optimising layout designs for wind or solar farms. Generative AI have a lot of potential to accelerate innovation.

IV. 4. AI FOR POLICY DESIGN AND URBAN ENERGY PLANNING

AI will become essential for policy formulation and urban planning. AI will help to model energy demand, grid behaviour, and renewable generation under different climatic scenarios or regulatory conditions. For example, subsidy models, peak pricing schemes, or battery deployment strategies are evaluated by reinforcement learning and optimisation algorithms in smart cities.

IV. 5. AI-INTEGRATED IOT AND 5G FOR SMART ENERGY NETWORKS

An AI model can get real-time data through IoT sensors, which are embedded in wind turbines, solar panels, home appliances and batteries. When 5G comes in this combination, it provides very fast decision making and control also for the large geographical area. In the future, fault detection, demand-response actions execution in less time, and energy flows coordination will be done through federated learning and swarm intelligence. It will help to make more efficient, resilient and adaptable smart grids.

V. CONCLUSION

The combination of Artificial intelligence and renewable energy systems has escalated improvement in the accuracy of prediction, grid management, efficiency in operations and energy storage. This paper described various real-world applications of Artificial Intelligence in the domain of renewable energy, including predictive maintenance, grid operations, and energy trading. Having said that, the adoption of AI in the energy sector is restricted due to interpretability problems, data scarcity, integration with old infrastructure, also the cybersecurity risks. However, future research models like Explainable AI, Edge computing, and Generative AI show promise for future improvement. The combination of Artificial Intelligence will play an important role for more sustainability, accuracy and smarter energy systems.

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